

DID YOU KNOW?

happy

THIS IS ONE OF SPOTIFY'S
RECOMMENDED MOODS FOR YOU

DID YOU KNOW?

sad

THIS IS ONE OF SPOTIFY'S
RECOMMENDED MOODS FOR YOU

DID YOU KNOW?

excited

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DID YOU KNOW?

relaxed

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anxious

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stressed

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content

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reflective

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confident

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inquisitive

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playful

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grateful

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inspired

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motivated

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irritated

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amused

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peaceful

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optimistic

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pensive

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enthusiastic

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